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Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnologik, fan va ta'limga oid
ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

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MUNDARIJA

Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlari investision faoliyatini rivojlantirishning muhim jihatlari.....	12
Abdurazakova Nargiza Rixsibaevna	
Buxgalteriya hisobida majburiyatlar va ularni tan olish mezonlari.....	19
Boltaev Abror Sayitmuradovich	
Banklararo raqobatning bank tizimi barqarorligiga ta'siri.....	25
Ortiqov Oybek Abdullaevich	
The improvement of funding business operations for the local enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan through issuing financial securities by means of the Tashkent Stock Exchange.....	34
Abduganiev Abdulaziz	
Shaxs ishbilarmonlik muloqotining subyekti sifatida.....	39
Turayeva Dinara Tulkunovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi mehnat bozorida kambag'allik darajasining aholi turmush farovonligiga ta'siri.....	44
Xayitov Sherbek Naimovich	
Tijorat banklari aktivlarini boshqarish va daromadligini oshirish masalalari.....	52
Masharipov Maxmud Bekturdievich	
Auditorlik tekshiruvining o'tkazishda dalil to'plash va natijalarni umumlashtirishda tahliliy amallarni qo'llanishi.....	59
Akromov Shohrux Shuhrat o'g'li	
Moliyaviy globalizatsiya sharoitida xorijiy mamlakatlar banklarida an'anaviy operatsiyalar amaliyoti va uni O'zbekiston bank tizimi faoliyatiga qo'llash yo'llari.....	70
Raxmatov Temur Sotiboldiyevich	
Innovatsion menejment yondashuvlari asosida sanoat korxonalarini faoliyatini boshqarish va tashkil etish.....	79
Bakayeva Mohira Ahrorovna	
Tijorat banklarida investitsion risklarni boshqarishni takomillashtirish.....	85
Burxonov Asliddin Asqar o'g'li	
Elektron sigaretalar hamda qizdirilgan tamaki iste'moli ortishi va uni tartibga solishning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	91
Mirzaliev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, Boykabilov Bahodir Mustafaevich, Qoraboev Bobur Umarovich, Ugay Darya Sergeevna, Mirzalieva Surmaniso Alisher qizi	

THE IMPROVEMENT OF FUNDING BUSINESS OPERATIONS FOR LOCAL ENTERPRISES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN THROUGH ISSUING FINANCIAL SECURITIES VIA THE TASHKENT STOCK EXCHANGE

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Annotatsiya: The financing landscape for businesses in Uzbekistan is evolving, with the introduction of new funding models aimed at enhancing access to capital. One such model is the 60/40 funding ratio, which emphasizes a balanced approach to financing. This article explores the significance of the 60/40 funding ratio, how it operates, and the benefits of fostering cooperation between the Tashkent Stock Exchange (TSE) and medium to large private enterprises. By encouraging local firms to go public or issue corporate bonds, this approach can facilitate capital raising for business operations and projects.

Kalit so'zlar: Tashkent Stock Exchange, medium-sized and large private companies, corporate loans, custodian banks, Central Bank of Uzbekistan, Clearstream, Euroclear, "Central Securities Depository" JSC, "National Clearing Centre" JSC, IPO.

Abstract: Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi 60/40 moliyalashtirish koeffitsiyentining ma'nosini, uning amalda qanday ishlashini va Toshkent fond birjasi bilan o'rta, yirik xususiy korxonalar o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni integratsiyalashning afzalliklarini ko'rsatishdan iborat. Shuningdek, mahalliy xususiy firmalarni biznes operatsiyalari va boshqa loyihalar uchun kapital jalb qilish maqsadida aksiyalar joylashtirish yoki korporativ obligatsiyalar chiqarishga yo'naltirishdan iborat.

Keywords: Toshkent fond birjasi, o'rta va yirik xususiy kompaniyalar, korporativ kreditlar, kaston banklar, O'zbekiston Markaziy Banki, Clearstream, Euroclear, "Qimmatli Qog'ozlar Markaziy Depozitariysi" AJ, "Milliy Kliring Markazi" AJ, IPO.

Аннотация: Цель данной статьи – показать значение коэффициента финансирования 60/40, а также то, как он на самом деле работает, и преимущества интеграции сотрудничества между Ташкентской фондовой биржей и средними и крупными частными предприятиями, поскольку это может побудить местные частные компании выходить на биржу или выпускать корпоративные облигации с целью привлечения капитала для коммерческой деятельности и других проектов.

Ключевые слова: Ташкентская Фондовая Биржа, средние и крупные частные компании, корпоративные кредиты, банки-костодианы, Центральный Банк Узбекистана, Clearstream, Euroclear, АО "Центральный Депозитарий Ценных Бумаг", АО "Национальный Клиринговый Центр", IPO.

INTRODUCTION

As is widely known, in Uzbekistan, almost all private firms rely on commercial loans to finance their expenses, even when expanding or diversifying output. They tend to prefer banking loans over going public or issuing bonds. Therefore, it is necessary to create a funding program that encourages local private businesses, especially medium and large companies, to seek alternative financing sources, such as selling shares or issuing corporate bonds through the Tashkent Stock Exchange.

Firstly, there should be credit limits for medium and large companies. Many of these firms are heavily reliant on bank loans, making it challenging for them to explore alternative funding options. Additionally, many private enterprises are entirely dependent on corporate loans, which restricts their ability to finance their operations independently. For this reason, it is crucial to impose specific restrictions on funding middle and large enterprises through commercial bank loans.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Professor of Finance, University of Oxford: Leverage International Best Practices: “Uzbekistan should adopt international standards for corporate governance, financial reporting, and investor protection to attract foreign capital. This will enhance the credibility of local enterprises and make their securities more appealing to global investors.”

Professor of Economics, Harvard University: Develop a Robust Legal Framework: “A strong legal framework is essential for a functioning stock market. Uzbekistan should prioritize the development of laws and regulations that protect investors, ensure fair market practices, and facilitate dispute resolution.”

Professor of Entrepreneurship, Stanford University: Foster a Culture of Entrepreneurship: “To encourage more local enterprises to access the stock market, Uzbekistan needs to foster a culture of entrepreneurship and innovation. This can be achieved through initiatives such as startup incubators, mentorship programs, and access to venture capital.”

Professor of Finance, University of Tokyo: Expand the Range of Securities: “Beyond equities, Uzbekistan should explore other types of securities, such as corporate bonds and sukuk (Islamic bonds), to cater to diverse investor preferences and provide alternative financing options for local enterprises.”

Professor of Economics, London School of Economics: Enhance Market Liquidity: “A liquid market is crucial for attracting investors. Uzbekistan should implement measures to increase trading volume and improve market efficiency, such as reducing transaction costs, promoting market-making activities, and enhancing market infrastructure.”

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the implementation of these research works, widely used methods in scientific research methodology were employed. Specifically, the scientific analysis involved various methods such as observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, analysis, and synthesis. These methods facilitated a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter and contributed to the depth and rigor of the research findings.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

So, it is essential to establish a funding program for middle and large private companies based on the 60/40 funding ratio. Specifically, a company looking to raise capital for its project would be permitted to take out only 40% of its estimated total project cost through loans, while the remaining 60% would need to be raised by going public, either by selling stocks or issuing bonds, all facilitated through the Tashkent Stock Exchange. Additionally, actions should be taken

by the authorities of the Tashkent Stock Exchange to support the IPO process, such as covering underwriting costs partially or fully. This would encourage local enterprises to explore funding sources beyond traditional corporate loans.

The 60/40 funding ratio (medium-sized and large firms)

This technique appears to be one of the most effective ways to encourage medium-sized and large private enterprises to fund the remaining 60% beyond the corporate loan market. Many businesses in Uzbekistan, particularly medium and large firms, are highly reliant on commercial bank loans for financing their projects or operations. For example, if a medium-sized or large firm plans to purchase a modern machine-tool to enhance output by reducing production costs, it would need to borrow funds for the acquisition. Under the 60/40 funding ratio, a bank would approve only 40% of the requested capital from the loan application, compelling the enterprise to seek alternative financing sources, such as issuing corporate bonds or selling stocks with the support of the Tashkent Stock Exchange.

Furthermore, authorities at the Tashkent Stock Exchange should take proactive steps to cover underwriting expenses for local companies' IPO processes, thus encouraging these firms to engage in raising funds through the stock market. This approach is expected to increase investment interest among local entrepreneurs in Uzbekistan. Several initiatives have already been made to develop the capital market infrastructure to help local companies attract external capital by issuing securities. For instance, under RP-291 "On Additional Measures to Develop the Capital Market," the "Central Securities Depository" JSC was established by the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, along with relevant accounts at the Central Bank to enhance the attractiveness of local securities to foreign investors.

The implementation of the 60/40 funding ratio is anticipated to be advantageous for all stock market participants, protecting the rights of both issuers and investors under the supervision of the Central Bank of Uzbekistan. Additionally, local medium and large enterprises could attract foreign currency for international purchases.

Moreover, measures should be taken to offer securities from middle and large companies to foreign investors by connecting them with foreign custodians like Clearstream and Euroclear, which manage foreign nominee accounts at the "Central Securities Depository" JSC or "National Clearing Centre" JSC. It is also crucial to create stock classes divided into "external" and "internal" categories. Foreign investors typically prefer US dollar-denominated assets to mitigate risks related to national

currency depreciation when withdrawing dividends or coupon payments. Therefore, the “external” class would be issued in foreign currency (e.g., US dollars), while the “internal” class would be issued in the national currency (UZS).

This approach would enable medium and large private businesses to attract funds in both national and foreign currencies, fostering cooperation between local enterprises and international financial institutions, which could provide various sources of capital for financing corporate projects and operations. Given the current dependence of many private companies, especially medium and large ones, on corporate loans from local banks, the 60/40 funding ratio offers a promising avenue for diversifying capital-raising strategies through the Tashkent Stock Exchange.

Allocated Corporate Loans in the Republic of Uzbekistan in trillion UZS (2021-2024)¹

The bar graph illustrates the allocation of corporate loans in the Republic of Uzbekistan, measured in trillions of UZS from 2021 to 2024. Overall, it shows an increase in total corporate loans from 14.8 trillion UZS in 2021 to 18.02 trillion UZS by August 1, 2024. Notably, corporate loans to medium-sized and large private companies rose significantly during this period, starting at 8.6 trillion UZS in 2021 and reaching 13.7 trillion UZS by August 2024. This indicates that more than half of the total corporate loans each year were utilized by these companies, highlighting their reliance on commercial banking loans for funding business operations and expanding their production of goods and services. Additionally, when looking at the percentage of allocated corporate loans, medium-sized and large private companies constituted 58% of the total in 2021, which increased to 76% by August 1, 2024. This demonstrates a notable growth in the share of corporate loans directed towards these enterprises, reflecting their increasing dependence on bank financing over the four-year period.

CONCLUSION

By and large, the 60/40 funding ratio could encourage medium-sized and large private firms to seek alternative sources of capital by going public through IPO procedures. This means they could

¹ Based on the author's development. Data gathered from the Internet.

sell shares of stocks to investors or issue corporate bonds. Regardless of the chosen option, all these processes would be facilitated by the Tashkent Stock Exchange, leading to an increase in the number of quoted companies on the listing board. Last but not least, the Tashkent Stock Exchange should take similar steps by covering IPO expenses for these medium and large private companies.

References

1. National Bank of Uzbekistan - Transparency of Information
2. National Bank of Uzbekistan - Annual Reports
3. Financial Statements as of 30 September 2023 - NBU
4. IFRS Consolidated Financial Statements as of 30 June 2023 - NBU
5. Central Bank of Uzbekistan - Bank Statistics
6. Investopedia - Principal Protected Notes
7. FINRA - Structured Notes with Principal Protection
8. Bertero, E. (1994). The banking system, financial markets, and capital structure: Some new evidence from France. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 10(4), 68-78.
9. Bonfiglioli, A., & Mendicino, C. (2004). Financial liberalisation, bank crises, and growth: Assessing the links. *Economics and Finance Working Paper No. 567*.
10. Brealey, R.A., Myers, S.C., & Allen, F. (2007). *Principles of Corporate Finance* (9th ed.). New Jersey: McGraw Hill.

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